

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Exploring the transcriptional program that instructs remodelling of the branchial arches (BA) in the heart

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

Created by

Munazah
Andrabi

[0000-0002-7718-5109](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7718-5109)

Based on

Based on Standard DMP template for Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) 2024

Funded by the [ELIXIR-UK: FAIR Data Stewardship training UKRI award \(MR/V038966/1\)](#) and [BioFAIR](#)

(Q1) Proposal name

Exploring the transcriptional program that instructs remodelling of the branchial arches (BA) in the heart.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This is a genomic and transcriptomic study of heart development using a mouse model at various stages of embryonic development with ChIP-Seq and bulk RNA-Seq.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

The study will generate sequencing data, i.e. ChIP-Seq to identify epigenetic modification (H3K27AC) of Meis transcription factor and RNA-Seq to understand the gene expression. Both raw and processed data will be generated.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

New mice cell lines will be developed from embryos between developmental stages E10.5 and E11.5 to carry out the ChIP-Seq and RNA-Seq experiments. The new cell lines will be deposited to ECACC together with detailed metadata. Data from ChIP-Seq and RNA-Seq experiments will be analysed to understand the underlying mechanism of BA development.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Chip-Seq experiment will be performed in duplicate for H3K27Ac and Meis transcription factor. RNA-Seq will also be performed in duplicate. For each experiment, paired-end sequencing will be done with each read of 75 bp in length. Raw data will be saved in the FASTQ format (format definition: doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp1137), and processed data will be in the form of images (.svg) and csv files. Each experiment of Chip-Seq and RNA-Seq will generate around 100 Gb of unprocessed data, depending on the depth of sequencing. The processed data will create 200-300 Gb of data.

Various software tools like FastQC, Trimmomatic, Tophat, Bowtie will be used for quality check, trimming, and mapping of the Chip-Seq and RNA-Seq reads to the mouse genome. MACS2 will be used for peak calling and various R and Bioconductor packages, such as DeSeq2 for further downstream analysis of the RNA-Seq experiment.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Initially, data will be stored on the central computational facility provided by the Research IT at the University, which is backed up and snapshots are taken every 24 hrs to mitigate data loss. All the analysis of the raw data will also be carried out on the central computational facility accessed via encrypted user accounts assigned by the IT.

In the longer term, after publication, data will be submitted to public repositories, e.g. Array Express or GEO. Each dataset will be assigned a global unique identifier (accession number), which can be used in future references. Appropriate metadata will be associated with both raw and processed data.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

RNA-Seq and Chip-Seq data will be annotated in compliance with the community metadata standard MINSEQE model (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5706412),

In addition, metadata will also comply with the requirements of the public repository, e.g. ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress), in which data will be deposited for reuse and long-term preservation.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All raw data (FASTQ) generated from NGS experiments (RNA-Seq and Chip-Seq) will be stored on the central computational facility of the university and also made available via the public repository of choice. Processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be available to all via the public repository, ArrayExpress.

We will keep all important research data, along with the metadata, for at least 10 years, following the guidelines set by the BBSRC for maintaining high standards in scientific work.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be available to all via the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress).

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be shared publicly via ArrayExpress immediately after publication. Data will also be made available upon request to the authors.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be available to all via the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress). Array Express assigns a unique identifier, called the Accession number, to each dataset which can be searched and referenced in future.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Metadata required for appropriate reuse (MINSEQE) will accompany all data submitted to the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress).

All details of the software (including versions) used, analysis pipelines will also be described in the methodology associated with the publication.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

We do not expect to have any restrictions or delays to data sharing. Data will be shared publicly via ArrayExpress immediately after publication.

(Q14) Secondary use

Data will be freely used for secondary analysis by the research community after its public release post publication. New data generated from this will help researchers better understand the developmental process of heart arteries.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

None

(Q16) Main risks to data security

Both the RNA-Seq and ChIP-Seq data generated from mouse embryos do not need to go through any kind of encryption or anonymisation.

(Q17) Capabilities

The University provides a safe and secure computational environment and storage supported by University staff.

The University also provides support to implement effective data management plans across different projects. No extra costs are anticipated for access to data and software beyond those included in the project application.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

Data management will be a standing item on the weekly project meetings and will be visited whenever new data is produced or collected to ensure compliance with effective data management policies and FAIR principles.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University is committed to zero direct carbon emissions by 2038 and has taken various measures to achieve that. It uses the Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework (LEAF) guidance framework to improve the sustainability and efficiency of research and laboratory spaces.